

Causes and Impact of Wars on the Oil and Gas Industry: Lessons from the Russia - Ukraine War 2022

Folarin Dimowo, PhD,¹ & Tolulope Alli.²

¹Folarin Dimowo, PhD.

Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Law, University of Benin, Nigeria.

Corresponding author. Email: folarin.dimowo@uniben.edu

²Tolulope Ali.

University of Benin, Nigeria.

Email: tolulopealli7@gmail.com

Abstract:

The Russia-Ukraine War, which erupted in 2022, and other wars, have had profound causes and far-reaching impacts on the global oil and gas industry, underscoring the vulnerability of energy markets to geopolitical instability. This research work aims to examine the causes and impacts of various wars on the oil and gas industry, with a great focus on the Russia-Ukraine war. It looks into the underlying causes of the war and its multi-dimensional consequences on the oil and gas sector, including sharp fluctuations in global prices, supply shortages, reconfiguration of energy alliances, and the acceleration of energy diversification strategies among European nations. It adopts a doctrinal approach in the examination of its subject matter, by relying on library and online sourced materials. The research will also discuss how other conflicts, have historically influenced the global energy market. It will explain how wars cause uncertainty, disrupt production and transportation routes, and lead to new policies by countries seeking to protect their energy security. A special focus will be placed on how European nations have responded to the Russia-Ukraine conflict by reducing their dependence on Russian oil and gas and investing more in renewable energy. By doing all these, this work will help readers understand the strong link between wars and the stability of global energy supply, showing why it is important for countries to plan for energy resilience in times of conflict.

Keywords: Energy, Conflict, Oil, Gas, Inflation.

Suggested Citation: F. Dimowo & T. Alli (2025), 'Causes and Impact of Wars on the Oil and Gas Industry: Lessons from the Russia - Ukraine War 2022,' *TzJMS*. Vol. 3. No. 1. pp. 33-49.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution

International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

The Russia's invasion of Ukraine has shaken global energy markets. The February incursion and the sanctions subsequently imposed on Moscow by the United States and the European Union have contributed to high oil and natural gas prices, complicating the global economic recovery from the coronavirus pandemic and exacerbating high inflation levels across the globe.¹ Russia is a significant actor in the global energy supply chain, as a major producer and exporter of oil and natural gas. Its energy exports play a particularly important role in European energy markets and are a major component of the European Union's energy security. Russia supplies the bulk of the EU's natural gas consumption, with the EU importing 155 billion cubic meters of natural gas, accounting for 45% of EU natural gas imports and 40% of total consumption.²

The far-reaching consequences of Russia's invasion of Ukraine for energy markets and geopolitics raise an important question: what implications does the Ukraine conflict have for European energy security, and what broader ramifications do those developments have for global energy policies? The experts of the Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU) of the Economists Group, London, the outbreak of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine affected the global Economy via three main channels: financial sanctions, commodities prices and supply chain disruptions.³ At the beginning of Russia invasion of Ukraine, even before the United States and the United Kingdom barred Russian oil and gas imports, some countries had ceased their purchases whilst others were panic-buying, and as result, prices soared to a 14-year high of USD 140 a barrel on 7th March, 2022.⁴ Russia supplies 14% of global production accounting for 7 – 8 million barrels per day of crude oil markets worldwide. The ban by the US and UK and the decision of some other pro-Ukraine countries to restrict the purchase of Russian crude oil further aggravated this crisis.

2. CAUSES OF THE RUSSIA INVASION

After the dissolution of the Soviet Union (USSR) in 1991, Ukraine and Russia maintained close ties. In 1994, Ukraine agreed to accede to the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons as a non-nuclear-weapon state.⁵ Former Soviet nuclear weapons in Ukraine were removed and dismantled. In return, Russia, the United Kingdom, and the

¹ Vincent Obisie-Orlu Exploring key implications of the Russia – Ukraine war on Africa's energy policy <https://afripoli.org/exploring-key-implications-of-the-russia-ukraine-war-on-africas-energy-policy> June 2nd, 2022 accessed 21st June,2024

² Ibid

³ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 22nd June,2024

⁴ Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) website, March,2022 accessed 22nd June,2024

⁵ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in Budjeryn, Mariana (21 May 2021). "Revisiting Ukraine's Nuclear Past Will Not Help Secure Its Future". *Lawfare*. Archived from the original on 13 January 2024. Retrieved 16 January 2024. Accessed on 25th June,2024

United States agreed to uphold the territorial integrity and political independence of Ukraine through the Budapest Memorandum on Security Assurances.⁶ In 1999, Russia was one of the signatories of the Charter for European Security, which "reaffirmed the inherent right of each and every participating State to be free to choose or change its security arrangements, including treaties of alliance, as they evolve."⁷ In the years after the dissolution of the USSR, several former Eastern Bloc countries joined NATO, partly in response to regional security threats involving Russia such as the 1993 Russian constitutional crisis, the War in Abkhazia (1992–1993) and the First Chechen War (1994–1996). Putin said Western powers broke promises not to let any Eastern European countries join NATO.⁸

At the 2008 Bucharest summit, Ukraine and Georgia sought to join NATO. The response among NATO members was divided. Western European countries opposed offering Membership Action Plans (MAP) to Ukraine and Georgia in order to avoid antagonizing Russia, while US President George W. Bush pushed for their admission.⁹ NATO ultimately refused to offer Ukraine and Georgia MAPs, but also issued a statement agreeing that "these countries will become members of NATO" at some point. Putin strongly opposed Georgia and Ukraine's NATO membership bids.¹⁰ By January 2022, the possibility of Ukraine joining NATO remained remote.

NATO and Russia had co-operated until Russia annexed Crimea 2014. In his 2022 speech justifying the invasion of Ukraine, Putin falsely claimed that NATO military infrastructure was being built up inside Ukraine and was a threat to Russia.¹¹ Russian Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov characterized the conflict as a proxy war started by

⁶ Ibid. quoted in Harahan, Joseph P. (2014). "With Courage and Persistence: Eliminating and Securing Weapons of Mass Destruction with the Nunn-Lugar Cooperative Threat Reduction Programs" (PDF). *DTRA History Series*. Defense Threat Reduction Agency. ASIN B01LYEJ56H. Archived from the original (PDF) on 28 February 2022. Retrieved 7 March 2022.

⁷ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in "Istanbul Document 1999". *Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe*. 19 November 1999. Archived from the original on 1 June 2014. Retrieved 21 July 2015. Accessed on 25th June, 2024

⁸ Ibid. Hall, Gavin E. L. (14 February 2022). "Ukraine: the history behind Russia's claim that Nato promised not to expand to the east". *The Conversation*. Archived from the original on 15 March 2022. Retrieved 14 March 2022.

⁹ Ibid. quoted in Brown, Colin (3 April 2008). "EU allies unite against Bush over Nato membership for Georgia and Ukraine". *The Independent*. p. 24. Accessed on 25th June, 2024

¹⁰ Ibid. quoted in Evans, Michael (5 April 2008). "President tells summit he wants security and friendship". *The Times*. p. 46. President Putin, in a bravura performance before the world's media at the end of the Nato summit, warned President Bush and other alliance leaders that their plan to expand eastwards to Ukraine and Georgia 'didn't contribute to trust and predictability in our relations'. Accessed on 25th June, 2024

¹¹ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in "Fact check: Russia's disinformation campaign targets NATO". *Deutsche Welle*. 13 February 2023. Accessed 25th June, 2024

NATO. He said: "We don't think we're at war with NATO ... Unfortunately, NATO believes it is at war with Russia".¹²

NATO says it is not at war with Russia; its official policy is that it does not seek confrontation, but rather its members support Ukraine in "its right to self-defense, as enshrined in the UN Charter".¹³ In 2022, NATO has condemned Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 'the strongest possible terms', and calls it 'the biggest security threat in a generation' which led to deployment of additional NATO units in its eastern members. Former CIA director Leon Panetta told the ABC that the U.S. is 'without question' involved in a proxy war with Russia.¹⁴

Russian military aircraft flying over the Baltic and Black Seas often do not indicate their position or communicate with air traffic controllers, thus posing a potential risk to civilian airliners. NATO aircraft scrambled many times to track and intercept these aircraft near alliance airspace. The Russian aircraft intercepted never entered NATO airspace, and the interceptions were conducted in a safe and routine manner. No formal declaration of war has been issued in the ongoing Russo-Ukrainian War. When Putin announced the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine, he claimed to commence a "special military operation", side-stepping a formal declaration of war.¹⁵ The statement was, however, regarded as a declaration of war by the Ukrainian government and reported as such by many international news sources.¹⁵ While the Ukrainian parliament refers to Russia as a "terrorist state" in regard to its military actions in Ukraine, it has not issued a formal declaration of war on its behalf.¹⁶

The Russian invasion of Ukraine violated international law (including the Charter of the United Nations). The invasion has also been called a crime of aggression under international criminal law¹⁷ and under some countries' domestic criminal codes – including those of Ukraine and Russia – although procedural obstacles exist to prosecutions under these laws.¹⁷

¹² Ibid. quoted in "Russia doesn't consider itself to be at war with NATO, Lavrov says". *Washington Post*. 29 April 2022. Accessed on 25th June, 2024

¹³ Ibid. quoted in "NATO-Russia: Setting the record straight". NATO. Retrieved 16 May 2023. Accessed on 25th June, 2024

¹⁴ Ibid. quoted in Macmillan, *Jade* (25 March 2022). "With NATO and the US in a 'proxy war' with Russia, ex-CIA boss Leon Panetta says Joe Biden's next move is crucial". Australian Broadcasting Corporation. Accessed on 25th June, 2024

¹⁵ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in Sheftalovic, *Zoya* (24 February 2022). "Battles flare across Ukraine after Putin declares war". Politico Europe. Archived from the original on 24 February 2022. Retrieved 22 April 2022. Accessed on 26th June, 2024

¹⁶ Ibid. "Verkhovna Rada recognized Russia as a terrorist state". *ukrinform.net*. 15 April 2022. Archived from the original on 18 April 2022. Retrieved 24 January 2024.

¹⁷ Ibid. Dannenbaum, Tom (10 March 2022). "Mechanisms for Criminal Prosecution of Russia's Aggression Against Ukraine". *Just Security*. Archived from the original on 16 April 2022. Retrieved 14 March 2022. Accessed 26th June, 2024

Until 2014 Ukraine was the main transit route for Russian natural gas sold to Europe, which earned Ukraine about US\$3 billion a year in transit fees, making it the country's most lucrative export service.¹⁸ Following Russia's launch of the Nord Stream pipeline, which bypasses Ukraine, gas transit volumes steadily decreased.¹ Following the start of the Russo-Ukrainian War in February 2014, severe tensions extended to the gas sector.¹⁹ The subsequent outbreak of war in the Donbas region forced the suspension of a project to develop Ukraine's own shale gas reserves at the Yuzivska gas field, which had been planned as a way to reduce Ukrainian dependence on Russian gas imports.²⁰ Eventually, the EU commissioner for energy Günther Oettinger was called in to broker a deal securing supplies to Ukraine and transit to the EU.²¹

An explosion damaged a Ukrainian portion of the Urengoy–Pomary–Uzhhorod pipeline in Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast in May 2014. Ukrainian officials blamed Russian terrorists.²² Another section of the pipeline exploded in the Poltava Oblast on 17 June 2014, one day after Russia limited the supply of gas to Ukrainian customers due to non-payment. Ukraine's Interior Minister Arsen Avakov said the following day that the explosion had been caused by a bomb.

In 2015, Russian state media reported that Russia planned to completely abandon gas supplies to Europe through Ukraine after 2018.²³ Russia's state-owned energy giant Gazprom had already substantially reduced the volumes of gas transited across Ukraine, and expressed its intention to reduce the level further by means of transit-diversification pipelines (Turkish Stream, Nord Stream, etc.). Gazprom and Ukraine agreed to a five-year deal on Russian gas transit to Europe at the end of 2019.²⁴

In 2020, the TurkStream natural gas pipeline running from Russia to Turkey changed the regional gas flows in South-East Europe by diverting the transit

¹⁸ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in "Kyiv's gas strategy: closer cooperation with Gazprom or a genuine diversification". Centre for Eastern Studies. 15 July 2013. Archived from the original on 23 October 2013. Accessed on 26th June,2024

¹⁹ Ibid. "Russia, Ukraine escalate 'gas war' as Europe draws 'map of fear'". Al Jazeera. 27 November 2019. Accessed on 26th June,2024

²⁰ Ibid. *Gent, Stephen E. (2021). Market power politics: war, institutions, and strategic delays in world politics. New York: Oxford University Press. p. 159. ISBN 978-0-19-752984-3. OCLC 1196822660. Accessed on 26th June,2024*

²¹ Ibid. "Russia-Ukraine gas deal secures EU winter supply". BBC News. 31 October 2014. Accessed on 26th June,2024

²² Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in "Blast at Ukraine gas pipeline said due to bomb, security increased". Reuters. Kyiv. 18 June 2014. Retrieved 12 June 2022. Accessed on 26th June,2024

²³ Ibid. "Gas supplies to bypass Ukraine from 2019 — Gazprom". TASS. Retrieved 3 February 2022. Accessed on 26th June,2024

²⁴ Ibid. *Makogon, Sergiy (1 October 2021). "Europe is under attack from Putin's energy weapon". Atlantic Council. Accessed on 26th June,2024*

through Ukraine and the Trans Balkan Pipeline system.²⁵ In May 2021, the Biden administration waived Trump's CAATSA sanctions on the company behind Russia's Nord Stream 2 gas pipeline to Germany.²⁶ Ukrainian President Zelenskyy said he was "surprised" and "disappointed" by Joe Biden's decision. In July 2021, the U.S. urged Ukraine²⁷ not to criticize a forthcoming agreement with Germany over the pipeline.

In July 2021, Biden and German Chancellor Angela Merkel concluded a deal that the U.S. might trigger sanctions if Russia used Nord Stream as a "political weapon". The deal aimed to prevent Poland and Ukraine from being cut off from Russian gas supplies. Ukraine will get a \$50 million loan for green technology until 2024 and Germany will set up a billion dollar fund to promote Ukraine's transition to green energy to compensate for the loss of the gas-transit fees. The contract for transiting Russian gas through Ukraine will be prolonged until 2034, if the Russian government agrees.²⁸

In August 2021, Zelenskyy warned that the Nord Stream 2 natural gas pipeline between Russia and Germany was "a dangerous weapon, not only for Ukraine but for the whole of Europe." In September 2021, Ukraine's Naftogaz CEO Yuriy Vitrenko accused Russia of using natural gas as a "geopolitical weapon".²⁹ Vitrenko stated that "A joint statement from the United States and Germany said that if the Kremlin used gas as a weapon, there would be an appropriate response.

3. IMPACTS OF RUSSIA AND UKRAINE WAR ON OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

The Russia – Ukraine war is one war that has proven to the world that oil and gas is a huge negotiation tool in international diplomacy. Europe and some of the G7 countries were the major market for Russian oil and gas and indeed highly dependent on Russian oil and gas. This also invariably means that the G7 and European countries were the major source of Russian revenue on oil. According to the experts of the Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU) of The Economists Group, London, the outbreak of the conflict between Russia

²⁵ Ibid. "Russia Launches into New Export Territory with TurkStream Natural-Gas Pipeline". Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty. 7 January 2020. Accessed on 26th June, 2024

²⁶ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in "Putin-Biden Summit Set for June 16 in Geneva". *The Moscow Times*. 25 May 2021. Accessed on 26th June, 2024

²⁷ Ibid. Woodruff, Betsy Swan; Ward, Alexander; Desiderio, Andrew (20 July 2021). "U.S. urges Ukraine to stay quiet on Russian pipeline". *Politico*. Retrieved 21 July 2021. Accessed on 26th June, 2024

²⁸ Ibid. "Nord Stream 2: Ukraine and Poland slam deal to complete controversial gas pipeline". *Euronews*. 22 July 2021. Retrieved 17 August 2021. Williams, Aime; Olearchyk, Roman (21 July 2021). "Germany and US reach truce over Nord Stream 2 pipeline". *Financial Times*. Retrieved 13 September 2021. Accessed on 26th June, 2024

²⁹ Russo-Ukraine war- Wikipedia, <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/russo-ukrainina-war> , quoted in "Ukraine gas chief urges Europe to resist Russia pressure on Nord Stream 2". *Financial Times*. 1 November 2021. Accessed on 26th June, 2024

and Ukraine have affect the global economy via three main channels: financial sanctions, commodities prices and supply chain disruptions.³⁰

As a precautionary measure, the United States (US) and the European Union (EU) have previously adopted a cautious approach to sanctioning Russia. Trade ties between Russia and the EU make European policymakers reluctant to impose stringent measures on Russia, although this restraint has disappeared to some extent. However, measures to restrict Russia's energy exports are still off the table, reflecting fears in European capitals that sanctions of such a nature would send EU economies into recession.³¹ The US Treasury planned carve-outs from sanctions for Russian energy exports, and Russian banks involved in the energy trade will not be excluded from SWIFT. The economic impact of EU and US sanctions will therefore be small outside of Russia, although Western companies that are highly exposed to Russia still affected

This conflict is also having a serious economic impact, which may become worsened day by day the longer the war continues. Furthermore, this disaster comes at an extremely fragile time, when the international economy is on the road to recovery from the devastation of the COVID-19 pandemic, and thus hinder economic revival to some extent. It is also felt that the repercussions of the Russia–Ukraine conflict hold considerable economic risks, not only in the whole EU region but also throughout the world.³² The recent COVID-19 pandemic has negatively impacted the global economy, especially the oil industry. Crude oil prices have been rising ever since the build-up of Russia's special military operation in Ukraine in late 2021. This is because major crude oil-importing countries were apprehensive of the war breaking out between Russia and Ukraine, which would compel Western nations to put sanctions on purchasing crude oil from Russia.³³ During Russia's ongoing invasion of Ukraine, even before the United States (US) and the United Kingdom (UK) barred Russian oil and gas imports, some countries had ceased their purchases whilst others were panic-buying, and as result, prices soared to a 14-year high of USD 140 a barrel on 7th March 2022.³⁴ Russia supplies 14% of global production or 7–8 million barrels per day of crude oil to markets worldwide.

³⁰ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024

³¹ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024

³² Ibid. <https://blogs.imf.org>. accessed on 28th June,2024

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024

The ban by the US and the UK and the decision of some other pro-Ukraine countries to restrict the purchase of Russian crude oil further aggravated this crisis.³⁵

Russia and Ukraine are the major producers of various agricultural commodities such as wheat, corn, sunflower, etc., along with a number of metals and minerals such as cobalt, copper, iron ore, aluminums, crude oil, gasoline, etc. Commodity prices jumped due to three factors: fear of supply shortage, the lack of physical infrastructure and sanctions. As the global impact of sanctions is restricted, the EIU and the global market expect that the major effect of the Russia–Ukraine conflict on the global economy have been observed in the form of higher commodity prices.³⁶ On the other hand, it is expected that crude oil prices will remain above USD 100 per barrel due to this crisis. The threats of sanctions on Russian hydrocarbon exports and supply disruptions are to be considered the reasons why the world is losing existing market tightness. Now, it is an issue that little trade is being made with Russian oil out of concern for secondary sanctions from the US on financial transactions with Russian entities.³⁷

Again, according to some experts, Russia cut off and halts its gas supply to the European Union countries in the winter. The gas prices increased by at least 50% in year (2022), on top of a five-fold rise in 2021.³⁸ Next, the ongoing war has completely destroyed existing supply chains, which were already severely affected along with international trade because of the financials sanctions imposed by the US and other EU nations.³⁹ Multinational companies are also struggling to establish alternative means of continuing their trade with Russia. Moreover, this situation is further aggravated with the partial destruction of Ukrainian ports and transport infrastructure due to the ongoing.⁴⁰ The global inflation rate is also soaring high, primarily due to a steep hike in commodity prices. According to the EIU, the current year has experienced a high inflation rate which still increase the year 2024.

From the producers' end, this sharp rise in commodity prices had dramatically increase the inflation rate which neutralize the positive effect of higher commodity prices for the producers and suppliers of commodities across the globe.⁴¹ Brent crude oil price recorded an eight-year high of USD 140 in March 2022, which was exclusively due to the outbreak of the Russia–Ukraine war which disrupted global supply chains. Higher crude oil prices also raised serious concerns amongst the supply chain systems throughout the world which are now more concerned with tackling soaring inflation due to ongoing Russia–Ukraine conflict rather than undertaking a post-COVID-19 pandemic recovery.⁴² The negative impact of the war on the economy has been mostly experienced by Russia

³⁵ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024

³⁶ Ibid. <https://blogs.imf.org>. accessed on 28th June,2024

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024

⁴⁰ Ibid. <https://www.eiu.com/n/global-economic-implications-of-the-russia-ukraine-wa> . accessed 28th June,2024

⁴¹ Ibid. <https://www.eiu.com> accessed on 28th June,2024

⁴² Ibid

and Ukraine and both these countries are now passing through the stage of sharp recession. G7 countries are also feeling negative impacts to some extent because of their close trade links with Russia, the whole world not excluded from the negative impacts.⁴³

The Russia–Ukraine war has had an imperative impact on all world economies. In particular, the prices of all essential commodities including crude oil have soared to record heights, which have also negatively affected the economic growth of all countries. According to the reports published by the IMF, the Russia–Ukraine war has severely hampered the global economic recovery, with the UK being harshly affected than most countries.⁴⁴ The conflict is increasing food and fuel prices, which, according to the IMF, have further weakened global economic growth. Moreover, in its latest report, the IMF lowered its global forecast and its outlook for the UK, which implies that the UK was no longer be the fastest growing economy amongst the G7 but may be the slowest by 2023.⁴⁵

German banks also heavily on Russia for most of Germany’s natural gas imports, as it imports between approximately 60% and 70% of its energy from Russia.⁴⁶ However, natural gas makes up less than 20% of Germany’s energy mix for power production. Germany is almost completely dependent on Russian crude supplies via pipeline projects such as Nord Stream 1 and Nord Stream 2.⁴⁷ However, in the case of Italy, even as the European Union decided to reduce Russian crude oil imports by up to 90% by the end of the year 2022, Italy stood aside in implementing the sanctions and chose to escalate its crude oil imports from Russia.⁴⁸

An inflationary impact is one of the major consequences of this ongoing war. The rise in inflation has been more pronounced in emerging and developing countries, which severely affects the poorest and most vulnerable in society and contributes to increasing inequalities worldwide.⁴⁹ The present war has been accompanied by a sharp rise in inflation under pressure from food, energy and major commodity prices. Inflation has been rising throughout 2021 till date as the recovery drives demand and continues to disrupt many value chains; however, the war has accelerated it.⁵⁰ Therefore, the Russia–

⁴³ Ibid

⁴⁴ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024.

⁴⁵ Ibid. <https://www.imf.org/en/News/Articles/2022/03/05/pr2261-imf-staff-statement-on-the-economic-impact-of-war-in-ukraine>. accessed on 28th June, 2024

⁴⁶ Ibid

⁴⁷ Ibid. <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-44794688>. accessed 28th June, 2024

⁴⁸ Ibid. <https://apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-politics-economy-global-trade-b0c193007210592123112e2db1069461>. accessed 28th June,2024

⁴⁹ Bhaskar Bagchi Effect of crude oil price shocks on stock markets and currency exchange rates in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict: Evidence from G7 countries <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/16/2/64> accessed on 28th June,2024

⁵⁰ Ibid. <https://blogs.imf.org/2022/04/27/inflation-to-be-elevated-for-longer-on-war-demand-job-markets/>. Accessed on 28th June, 2024

Ukraine conflict has caused a double whammy to the global recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. Europeans and G7 countries are no exception.⁵¹

However, despite the imposition of Western sanctions, Russia continues to grow its crude oil production from the beginning of the invasion till date. The decline in access to Russian oil has only increased demand, pushing the oil price up further. Russia is making even more money from sales than it was, before the war started. And the value of its once-failing currency has risen versus the dollar, says the *New York Times*.⁵² Many Asian countries stepped in to acquire cheap crude from Russia. Demand from India, China, and Turkey has increased along with domestic market demand, diminishing upstream losses.

The Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan bought an estimated \$5.5bn of fossil fuels from Russia during the first five months of the invasion of Ukraine.⁵³ According to *Reuters*, Russia's earnings grew to \$337.5 bn in 2022, a 38% increase over 2021, as global demand for oil has helped to offset declining European demand.⁵⁴ The Russian exports during the war CREA's data shows that In the first half of the war, Russia's exports of fossil fuels generated revenues of \$151.8bn. The EU imported 54% of this, totaling around \$81.7bn. Since the beginning of the invasion, fossil fuel exports have provided around \$41.32bn to Russia's federal budget, helping to fund the war in Ukraine.⁵⁵

4. IMPACTS OF VARIOUS WARS ON OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

Oil has shaped international conflict for decades. According to one estimate, twenty-five to fifty percent of interstate wars between 1973 and 2012 had oil-related linkages.⁵⁶ But the cyclical nature of oil's contribution to global conflict is not well understood. Not only are oil prices cyclical, but the geopolitics of oil are linked inexorably to the same boom and bust price cycle. Military adventurism, proxy wars and regional pathologies in the Middle East expand and contract with the ebb and flow of massive petrodollar accumulations related to the oil price cycle.⁵⁷

The massive inflow of petrodollar revenues when oil prices are high creates disposable incomes that can be easily dispensed on regional arms races, especially since

⁵¹ Ibid. <https://www.imf.org/en/>. Accessed 28th June, 2024

⁵² Smruthi Nadig Before and after: how the Ukraine crisis has affected Russian oil <https://www.offshore-technology.com/feature/before-and-after-how-the-ukraine-crisis-has-affected-russian-oil/> October 3rd, 2022 accessed 17th July, 2024

⁵³ Ibid

⁵⁴ Ibid

⁵⁵ Ibid

⁵⁶ Amy Jaffe, Jareer Ellass War and the Oil price Cycle 14th February, 2016 quoted in Jeff D. Colgan, "Fueling the Fire: Pathways from Oil to War," *International Security*, Vo. 38, No. 2 (Fall 2013) 147-180. Accessed on 18th July, 2024

⁵⁷ Ibid

oil consuming countries like the United States are incentivized to increase arms sales as a means of solving oil import related trade deficits.⁵⁸ Besides transferring wealth from industrialized countries to oil producers in the Middle East and North African (MENA) region and Russia (and stimulating renewed drilling for oil and gas in North America), high global oil and natural gas prices also slow global economic growth and encourage energy conservation.⁵⁹ This causes petroleum demand to slow globally, lowering oil prices. Social and political problems in the region reemerge as oil prices recede. Regional governments have fewer resources to spend on restive populations that have become accustomed to generous handouts enabled by high oil prices. Job creation and visible social programs slow, dissatisfaction rises, and the consequences of economic downturns incite support for militants.⁶⁰ The ensuing instability forced governments to use newly purchased arms, which ironically begins the cycle yet again, as new conflicts disrupt oil supplies in the recent war between Russia and Ukraine'

In this manner, the world experiences perpetuating patterns of military conflict, followed by oil supply crises, and accompanying global financial instability. In effect, the Middle East resource curse has become globalized.⁶¹ The challenges this is presenting on humanitarian, security and economic fronts have become increasingly dangerous. The arms race that has accompanied the rise of oil prices over the 2000s has been no exception and is now all the more complicated due to the violent participation of sub-national radicalized groups that are less susceptible to diplomatic pressures or initiatives.⁶² In this emerging geopolitical context, the rise of violent sub national groups like ISIS and Al-Qaeda are increasingly putting oil infrastructure at risk, laying the groundwork for a future oil crisis that may prove harder to solve than in the past.⁶³

As borders and ruling institutions have become contested, so has control of the region's major oil and gas facilities. Initially an outgrowth of disunity inside Iraq, the conflict over oil and gas facilities is now accelerating across ungoverned territories, with important long-term consequences for global energy markets. Mideast oil and gas production capacity, along with surface facilities, are increasingly being damaged in ways

⁵⁸ Ibid

⁵⁹ Ibid

⁶⁰ Amy Jaffe, Jareer Elass War and the Oil price Cycle 14t February, 2016 quoted in Jeff D. Colgan, "Fueling the Fire: Pathways from Oil to War," *International Security*, Vo. 38, No. 2 (Fall 2013) 147-180. Accessed on 06th August,2024

⁶¹ Ibid

⁶² Ibid

⁶³ Ibid

that will make them hard to repair. Export disruptions, which were once sporadic, are becoming a more permanent feature of the civil war landscape.⁶⁴

4.1 Disruption of oil and gas supplies

The disruption of oil and gas supplies in international market usually spike prices upwards anytime oil related war occurred. Supply chain disruption represents a major threat to businesses in the oil & gas industry, and has a knock-on effect on the economic development of oil producing nations around the world.⁶⁵ Over the years, supply chains have become longer and more complex, while the severity and frequency of supply chain disruption is increasing. From political instability and violence caused by various wars. The oil & gas industry remains one of the most significant industries in the global economy, accounting for four of the world's top 10 companies by revenue in Fortune's 2017 Global 500 list. Oil is the world's leading fuel, with over 90 million barrels of crude oil produced every day⁶⁶ in countries including Saudi Arabia and Iran in the Middle East, parts of Russia and China in Asia, the US and Brazil in the Americas and Nigeria and Angola in Africa.

The disruptions in the oil and gas supply chain can occur at any stage of the distribution process. From exploration and production to transportation, storage, and distribution, each phase presents unique vulnerabilities.⁶⁷ According to industry data, approximately 75% of oil and gas companies experienced at least one supply chain disruption in the past year alone. These disruptions not only impact operational efficiency but also pose significant financial risks, with estimates suggesting that supply chain disruptions can cost companies millions of dollars in lost revenue and productivity annually.⁶⁸ The fears over energy sanctions and the ambiguity over the banking sanctions have already seen companies avoid purchasing Russian barrels, pushing prices to new multiyear highs and shaving-off shock mitigation policies such as the SPR releases. Also, it has become clear that traders holding Russian crude on their books are struggling to clear cargoes and this has been reflected in widening differentials and rising shipping and insurance costs.⁶⁹

⁶⁴ Amy Jaffe, Jareer Elass War and the Oil price Cycle 14t February, 2016 quoted in Jeff D. Colgan, "Fueling the Fire: Pathways from Oil to War," *International Security*, Vo. 38, No. 2 (Fall 2013) 147-180. Accessed on 06th August,2024

⁶⁵ Corporate Disputes, supply chain disruption in oil and gas industry. <https://www.corporatedisputiesmagazine.com/supply-chain-distruption-in-the-oil-gas-industry>. Accessed on 7th August,2024

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Linked in, Fueling the future supply chain disruptions in the oil and gas industry. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/fueling-future-supply-chain-distruptions-oil-gas-industry-ibb2f> published 11th March,2024. Accessed 7th August,2024

⁶⁸ Linked in, Fueling the future supply chain disruptions in the oil and gas industry. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/fueling-future-supply-chain-distruptions-oil-gas-industry-ibb2f> published 11th March,2024. Accessed 7th August,2024

⁶⁹ The Oxford institute for energy studies. Russia- Ukraine crisis: implications for global oil market. <https://www.oxfordenergy.org/publications/russia-ukraine-crisis-implications-for-global-oil-markets/> Accessed 7th August,2024

The supply chain disruptions of Russian crude supplies to West have affected by the following impacts

1. The massive shifts in trade flows and sharp adjustments in price differentials to reflect shifts in Russian crude exports. Particularly, there could be a greater re- redirection of flows from Europe to Asia, but there are limits to such re-direction and not all Urals previously destined to Europe will flow into Asia.⁷⁰
2. The Russian oil companies could offer sweeteners to buyers to make their barrels more attractive, for instance shifting cargoes from FOB to CFR basis. Also, in response to more extensive self-sanctioning, Urals and ESPO could be offered at discounts so large that cargoes would eventually clear, potentially as masked cargoes or via ship-to-ship transfers. But there are limits to this strategy given the large volumes of Russian exports and the intensification and widening of sanctions.⁷¹
3. The self-sanctioning escalates over the coming years since the war started leading to a reduction in Russian production and supply disruptions at a larger scale.⁷²

In the current environment of ever rising tensions, one should also not also exclude the possibility that in an escalation situation where Russia struggles to clear its barrels, weaponizing energy becomes the next chapter in Russia's ongoing standoff with the West. As these are still early days, a scenario in which Russian oil supplies get disrupted in a sudden manner should also be considered. This will exert significant pressure on both market balances and prices in the near-term and for most of 2022.⁷³

4.2 Higher global interest rates and energy prices

The impact of higher global interest rates and energy prices on economic growth and energy demand. The interest rates always remain higher and global energy demand prices always elevated each time oil war spiked⁷⁴. This can be seen in Russia Ukraine war where price of crude oil increase from around \$ 76 per barrel at the start of the war in January 2022 to over \$ 130 per barrel in March same year⁷⁵.

The 1973 energy crisis, also known as the Oil Shock of 1973–74, was a period of skyrocketing energy prices and fuel shortages resulting from an embargo by Arab oil-producing nations in response to U.S. support for Israel during the Yom Kippur War. During this period, the price of a barrel of oil nearly quadrupled in less than a year. The

⁷⁰ Ibid

⁷¹ The Oxford institute for energy studies. Russia- Ukraine crisis: implications for global oil market. <https://www.oxfordenergy.org/publications/russia-ukraine-crisis-implications-for-global-oil-markets/> Accessed 7th August,2024

⁷² Ibid

⁷³ Ibid

⁷⁴ EIU, War in the Middle East will keep hydrocarbon prices elevated <https://www.wiu.com/n/war-in-the-middle-east-will-keep-hydrocarbon-prices-elevated/> Accessed 9th/08/2024

⁷⁵ OPEC Website, March 2022

embargo was lifted in early 1974, but the economic shock it caused is regarded as a precursor to the rapid inflationary pressures and stagflation experienced later in the 1970s. The oil embargo of 1973 was just one of many complicating factors that led to a decade of high inflation and stagflation in the United States during the '70s.⁷⁶ On October, 19, 1973, following then-President Richard Nixon's decision to provide Israel with \$2.2 billion in emergency aid in support of the Yom Kippur War, the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) approved an oil embargo on the U.S. This effectively shut off the exports of Arab crude oil to the U.S., followed by a series of steep production cuts in output.⁷⁷

Before the embargo, a barrel of oil traded for around \$2.90, quadrupling to \$11.65 per barrel by January 1974.⁷⁸ This led to an increase in the price of regular gasoline in the U.S. from an average of 39 cents per gallon before the crisis to 53 cents in 1974, an increase of around 36% in less than a year.⁷⁹ As with most economic events, the 1973 energy crisis and inflation that followed were caused by several factors, not just U.S. support for Israel.

There had been a decades-long struggle between the governments of oil-producing nations and the large U.S. oil conglomerates for control over the global oil market.⁸⁰ Until the 1970s, OPEC, formed in 1960, had kept a relatively low profile, mainly negotiating with international oil companies for better terms for its member countries. OPEC saw the Yom Kippur War as a way to make its geopolitical power known and to strike a blow at the U.S. oil giants.⁸¹ Inflation, too, was not caused only by high energy prices. The U.S. saw commodity prices rise at a rate of around 10% per year starting in 1970, and inflation was on the Federal Reserve's radar of things to keep a close eye on even before 1973.⁸² The oil embargo only made things worse and sped up inflation.

⁷⁶ Adam Hayes, '1973 Energy crisis: causes and effects updated on 20th July,2023 quoted in Federal Reserve History "Oil Shock of 1973–74 <https://www.federalreservehistory.org/essay/oil-shock-of-1973> . Accessed on 10th August,2024

⁷⁷ Adam Hayes, '1973 Energy crisis: causes and effects updated on 20th July,2023 quoted in Federal Reserve History "Oil Shock of 1973–74 <https://www.federalreservehistory.org/essay/oil-shock-of-1973> . Accessed on 10th August,2024

⁷⁸ Ibid quoted in U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. "CPI Inflation Calculator https://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm. Accessed on 10th August,2024

⁷⁹ Ibid quoted in U.S. Energy Information Administration. "Total Energy: Annual Energy Review." <https://www.eia.gov/totalenergy/data/annual/showtext.php?ptb0524>. Accessed on 10th August,2024

⁸⁰ Ibid Francesco Petrini, via ResearchGate. "Eight Squeezed Sisters: The Oil Majors and the Coming of the 1973 Oil Crisis https://www.researchgate.net/profile/francesco-petrini-2/publication/259081793_eight_squeezed_sisters_the_oil_majors_and_the_coming_of_the_1973_oil_crisis. Accessed on 10th August,2024

⁸¹ Ibid

⁸² Adam Hayes, '1973 Energy crisis: causes and effects updated on 20th July,2023 quoted in Federal Reserve Archival System for Economic Research (FRASER), Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis. "The Anguish of Central Banking

4.3 Price volatility

The disruptions in oil and gas supplies and concerns about transit routes risks always lead to price volatility in global market. For instance, the Russia war against Ukraine. Ukraine is major transit route for the delivery of Russia natural gas to Europe and according to U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA)⁸³, in the first half of the war, Europe imported 54% of Russia oil accounted for \$ 81.7 Billion⁸⁴ which its use to power the economy through transporting en route Ukraine.

The term “price volatility” is used to describe price fluctuations of a commodity. Volatility is measured by the day-to-day percentage difference in the price of the commodity. The degree of variation, not the level of prices, defines a volatile market. Since price is a function of supply and demand, it follows that volatility is a result of the underlying supply and demand characteristics of the market. Therefore, high levels of volatility reflect extraordinary characteristics of supply and/or demand.⁸⁵ Prices of basic energy (natural gas, electricity, heating oil) are generally more volatile than prices of other commodities. One reason that energy prices are so volatile is that many consumers are extremely limited in their ability to substitute other fuels when the price, of natural gas for example, fluctuates. Residential customers usually cannot replace their heating system quickly--and in the long run, it may not be economical to do so. So, while consumers can substitute readily between food products when relative prices of foodstuffs change, most do not have that option in heating their homes.⁸⁶

Volatility provides a measure of price uncertainty in markets. When volatility rises, firms may delay investment and other decisions or increase their risk management activities. The costs associated with such activities tend to increase the costs of supplying and consuming gas.⁸⁷

It is commonly believed that since the 1973 oil crisis, oil and energy prices have been more volatile than other commodity prices. The energy volatility started in 1945 through up till date. The results show that crude oil, refined petroleum, and natural gas prices are more volatile than prices for about 95% of products sold by domestic producers. Relative to crude commodities, however, crude oil prices are currently more volatile than about 65% of other products, and oil price volatility first exceeded the median for crude

[https://www.fraser.stlouisfed.org/files/docs/publications/FRB/pages/1985-1989/32252_1985-1989.pdf?page688\(page2ofPDF\)](https://www.fraser.stlouisfed.org/files/docs/publications/FRB/pages/1985-1989/32252_1985-1989.pdf?page688(page2ofPDF)) .Accessed on 10th August,2024

⁸³ Michael T. Klane, Twenty – first century energy wars: how oil and gas fuelling global conflicts 15/07/2014. Accessed 04/02/2024

⁸⁴ Smruth Nadig, Before and after: how the Ukraine crisis has affected Russian oil. 03/10/2022

⁸⁵ https://www.eia.gov/naturalgas/weekly/archivenew_ngwu/2003/10_23/volatility%2010-22-03.htm. Accessed on 20th August,2024

⁸⁶ https://www.eia.gov/naturalgas/weekly/archivenew_ngwu/2003/10_23/volatility%2010-22-03.htm. Accessed on 20th August,2024

⁸⁷ Ibid

commodities following the 1986 drop in oil prices.⁸⁸ While oil and energy price volatility increased following the 1973 oil crisis, this was mirrored by an increase in price volatility for all products, which explains why fuels did not stand out in Clem's (1985) analysis. However, in the late 1970s, price volatility for most products returned to pre-1973 levels, while oil price volatility continued to increase. Oil price volatility surpassed most other crude commodities' price volatility in the mid-1980s and this pattern continues today.⁸⁹

The Russia-Ukraine War, which has lasted for over two years, it has been proven to significantly impact crude oil prices throughout the world. The Russia-Ukraine War affects crude oil prices, through its impact on speculative activities, inventory, and supply-demand balance, combined with production announcements of Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), led to sharp short-term fluctuations in international oil prices and rapid price increases. Among these channels, speculative activities, inventory, and supply have a substantial impact. Relevant entities can weaken the impact of the war on oil prices and macroeconomic factors by intervening in these transmission channels.⁹⁰

As the primary input in production processes, crude oil is of great importance due to its scarcity and strategic nature. Therefore, fluctuations in crude oil prices are of widespread concern to regulators and market participants. Additionally, as a highly financialized product, the spillover effects of crude oil price fluctuations on other commodity markets cannot be underestimated. However, in recent years, due to events such as COVID-19 and the Russia-Ukraine War, crude oil prices have shown a trend of high volatility and rapid changes. For instance, due to the impact of COVID-19, the West Texas Intermediate (WTI) crude oil futures price fell to a negative value for the first time on April 20, 2020. The Russia-Ukraine War and subsequent events led to a rapid increase in crude oil prices. On March 7, 2022, the WTI crude oil futures price reached 133.460 US dollars per barrel, and the Brent crude oil futures price reached 139.130 US dollars per barrel, the highest price since July 2008.⁹¹

⁸⁸ Eva Regnier. Oil and energy price volatility <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0140988305001118>. Accessed 20th August, 2024

⁸⁹ Eva Regnier. Oil and energy price volatility. <https://sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0140988305001118>. Accessed on 20th August, 2024

⁹⁰ Qi Zhang, Kun Yang and others. Unveiling the impacts of geopolitical conflict on oil prices: A case study of the Russia – Ukraine war and its channels volume 126, October 2023. <https://sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0140988323004541>. Accessed on 20th August, 2024

⁹¹ Qi Zhang, Kun Yang and others. Unveiling the impacts of geopolitical conflict on oil prices: A case study of the Russia – Ukraine war and its channels volume 126, October 2023. <https://sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0140988323004541>. Accessed on 20th August, 2024

5. RECOMMENDATION

1. The oil rich countries should in the face of evolving war driven market dynamics seek out and develop new export markets, Russia is currently doing this by venturing and cultivating the entire Asian market with the mega gas deal and supply to India and China markets. This diversification has helped Russia to minimize the effect of sanctions and bans by USA, Europe and the allies. The reliance on a single market for a nation's valuable commodities can be hurtful at time of war and crises. Therefore, diversification of customers is key to fiscal stability during hostilities.

2. There is need for oil producing countries to make use of their domestic currencies as pricing template for crude oil prices this will reduce the over dependence on US dollar or petrodollar hegemony enjoying by the USA for many years, there by strengthen other oil producing countries currencies.

3. The European countries must partner with gas exporting African countries to avoid fossil fuel lock-in, and pursue policies such as a carbon take back obligation – agreements placing the responsibility of the safe storage of CO₂ on the producers and importers of fossil fuels as African countries develop the infrastructure needed to increase gas export to Europe⁹².

4. There is need to develop more policies to support decarbonization and develop policies towards achieving a renewable energy. This will relief and protect our natural ecosystems that act as carbon sinks, technology transfer to support the development of low carbon energy technologies and transmission and also reduce frequent wars caused by oil and gas.

5.1 Conclusion

The Russia-Ukraine War of 2022 has shown how modern wars can badly affect the global oil and gas industry. The war caused major disruptions in energy supply and led to sharp changes in prices. Many countries, especially in Europe, had to quickly find new sources of energy and rethink their long-term plans. The conflict revealed the risks of depending too much on unstable regions for energy. It also pushed the world to invest more in renewable energy. Overall, this and similar wars remind us that energy security, smart planning, and global cooperation are key to a stable energy future.

⁹² Vincent Obisie-Orlu, Exploring key Implications of the Russia-Ukraine war on Africa's energy policy
<https://afripoli.org/exploring-key-implications-of-the-russia-ukraine-war-on-africas-energy-policy>. accessed on 18th October, 2024.